

Making academic publishing Open and FAIR: how MorphoBank aids data reproducibility

Mark T. Young^{1-3*}

¹ School of Biological Sciences, University of Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom; ² School of GeoSciences, University of Edinburgh, Edinburgh, United Kingdom; ³LWL-Museum für Naturkunde, Münster, Germany; ⁴ Natural History Museum, London, United Kingdom; ⁵ Department of Anatomy, New York Institute of Technology College of Osteopathic Medicine, Old Westbury, NY, USA; ⁶ Department of Paleontology, University of Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland; ⁷ Department of Geosciences, Auburn University, Auburn, Alabama 36849, USA; ⁸ Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), Departamento de Biología Facultad de Ciencias Exactas y Naturales, Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata, B7602AYL Mar del Plata, Argentina; ⁹ Institut Català de Paleontologia Miquel Crusafont (ICP-CERCA), Cerdanyola del Vallès, Barcelona, Spain; ¹⁰ School of Earth Sciences, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK; ¹² Grupo Aragosaurus-IUCA, Paleontología, Facultad de Ciencias, Universidad de Zaragoza, Zaragoza, Spain; ¹³ Jackson School of Geosciences, The University of Texas at Austin, USA; ¹⁴ Department of Biosciences, Swansea University, Swansea, United Kingdom; ¹⁵ Department of Earth Sciences, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB2 3EQ, United Kingdom; ¹⁶ Museum of Zoology, University of Cambridge, Cambridge CB2 3EJ, United Kingdom; ¹⁷ Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET), División Paleontología Vertebrados, Facultad de Ciencias Naturales y Museo, Universidad Nacional de la Plata, Paseo del Bosque s/n, B1900FWA, Argentina; ¹⁸ School of Geography and Planning, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou 510006, China; ¹⁹ Department of Ecology and Evolutionary Biology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, USA; ²⁰ Museum of Paleontology, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, USA; ²¹ Department of Organismic and Evolutionary Biology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA; ²² Museum of Comparative Zoology, Harvard University, Cambridge, MA 02138, USA; ²³ Turkana Basin Institute, Nairobi, Kenya; ²⁴ Departamento de Paleobiología, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales – CSIC, C/ José Gutiérrez Abascal 2, Madrid 28006, Spain; ²⁵ National Museum of Natural History, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine; ²⁶ University of Wrocław, Wrocław, Poland; ²⁷ MorphoBank, Phoenix Bioinformatics, Newark, CA, USA; ²⁸ Department of Chemistry, Biology, and Health Sciences, South Dakota School of Mines and Technology, Rapid City, SD, USA; ²⁹ Philadelphia College of Osteopathic Medicine – Georgia Campus, Suwanee, GA 30024, USA; ³⁰ Department of Environmental Biology, Sapienza University of Rome, Rome, Italy; ³¹ Universidade Federal de Santa Maria, São João do Polêsine, Brazil; ³³ Institut Català de Paleocologia Humana i Evolució Social (IPHES-CERCA), Tarragona, Spain; ³⁴ Millennium

Nucleus Early Evolutionary Transitions of Mammals, Santiago, Chile; ³⁵ Senckenberg Research Institute and Natural History Museum, Frankfurt am Main, 60325, Germany; ³⁶ Max Planck Institute of Geoanthropology, Jena, Germany; ³⁷ Australian Research Centre for Human Evolution, Griffith University, Nathan, Queensland, Australia; ³⁸ Department of Life Sciences, University of Lincoln, Lincoln, UK; ³⁹ Institute of Rock Structure and Mechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁴⁰ National Library of Technology, Prague, Czech Republic; ⁴¹ Franklin and Marshall College, Lancaster, PA, USA; ⁴² Universidad Tecnológica Nacional, Facultad Regional San Rafael, Instituto de Evolución, Ecología Histórica y Ambiente (IDEVEA), San Rafael, Argentina; ⁴⁴ Department of Science and Mathematics, Mount Aloysius College, Cresson, USA; ⁴⁵ Section of Vertebrate Paleontology, Carnegie Museum of Natural History, Pittsburgh, USA; ⁴⁶ School of Resources and Environment, Henan Polytechnic University, Jiaozuo 454003, China

* marktyoung1984@gmail.com

‡ All other co-authors are listed in alphabetical order

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The Open Science movement aims to make scientific research more transparent and accessible. Given the reproducibility crises and global inequity of data access, Open Science principles are more important than ever. Within an academic publishing setting, the Open Science framework makes the publication process more transparent and trustworthy, and normalises the sharing of data. We, the editorial board of the journal *Historical Biology*, are committed to Open Science and FAIR principles. *Historical Biology* is a hybrid open-access journal that publishes papers covering evolutionary and systematic biology through time, spanning both archaeology and palaeontology, and clades across the entire tree of life. We have recently undertaken a number of changes to refocus the journal, and as part of our commitment to Open and FAIR principles, we: 1) have introduced dedicated article types such as 'Data Note', 'Method', and 'Registered Reports'; 2) are now a PCI RR-Friendly journal; and 3) have introduced dedicated editorial roles (including a Data Editor and Phylogenetics Editor). These new editorial roles strengthen our ability to support authors in making their research reproducible and replicable, both by ensuring datasets are properly managed and that manuscripts adhere to Open Science practices, including pre-registration and the use of online repositories like MorphoBank. Moving forward, MorphoBank will be our recommended repository for phylogenetic datasets, particularly from 2026 when our data sharing policy shifts to 'Openly Available'. By promoting best practices for data management and collaboration with authors, *Historical Biology* aims to contribute to a more transparent and accessible scientific community.

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